

Synthesis of some plumbagin derivatives and their antibacterial activity

Saradha Vasanth^{*a}, K. Balakrishna^a, N. K. George^b and G. Veluchamy^a

^aCentral Research Institute for Siddha, Arumbakkam, Chennai-600 106, India

^bLoyola College, Chennai-600 034, India

Manuscript received 23 April 2003, accepted 12 January 2004

Several plumbagin derivatives were synthesized from plumbagin and tested for their antimicrobial activity.

The root of *Plumbago zeylanica* Linn. (Plumbaginaceae), commonly known as Chitraka in Sanskrit and Chitramoolam in Tamil has medicinal properties and used in indigenous system of medicine. The roots are caustic, abortifacient, expectorant and used in the treatment of tumours. It is useful in rheumatism, skin diseases, diarrhoea, dyspepsia, piles, scabies and ulcers^{1,2}. Besides plumbagin, a number of naphthaquinones have been reported from the roots of the plant³. Plumbagin has been reported to have various biological activities⁴. The present investigation aims at the isolation of plumbagin from the roots of *Plumbago zeylanica* and its conversion to synthetic analogues viz., 3-chloroplumbagin, 6-bromoplumbagin, acetyl plumbagin and its reductive acetylation product by standard procedures^{5,6} (Fig. 1).

5 Reductive acetylation product of plumbagin

Fig. 1. Plumbagin and its synthetic derivatives.

These compounds were studied for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus*, *Bacil-*

lus cereus, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella aerogenes* and *Shigella boydii* by steak plate method⁷ using chloramphenicol (30 µg/disc) as standard. The objective of the study is to find out the halogen substituent effect, the importance of the hydroxyl group and the quinone moiety against these bacterial strains.

Plumbagin and its derivatives were effective against *S. citreus* and *S. boydii* at the lowest concentration studied (i.e. 10 µg ml⁻¹) and were inactive to all other strains up to 40 µg ml⁻¹. The inhibition of activity of plumbagin against *S. citreus* was in accordance with earlier studies by Pandey *et al.*⁸. The reduction of the quinone system, reductive acetylation and substitution with chlorine and bromine did not alter the antibacterial effect since all the derivatives tested were equally effective and the MIC was found to be 10 µg ml⁻¹ in all cases.

Experimental

All m.ps. taken were uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1600 FTIR spectrophotometer and UV spectra in MeOH were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer λ-3 spectrophotometer. The ¹H NMR spectra in CDCl₃ were taken on a Varian 60 MHz spectrometer with TMS as the internal standard. The roots were purchased from the local market and identified at the Botany Department of Central Research Institute (Siddha), Chennai.

The shade dried root (1 kg) was cut, coarsely powdered and extracted with chloroform in the cold in an aspirator bottle (48 h). The extract was concentrated to a syrupy mass (200 g). It was steam distilled when plumbagin was collected in the distillate and it was kept overnight in the fridge. The orange red solid formed was filtered, dried and recrystallised from hexane, m.p.78° (1 g). It gave a single spot on TLC over silica gel with hexane-benzene (1 : 1) as developing solvent (R_f 0.45). It

gave deep red colour on ferric reaction and pink colour with NaOH. It was identified as plumbagin (1) viz. 5-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone by m.p, m.m.p. and Co-TLC with authentic sample.

This material was used for synthesis of other derivatives.

6-Bromoplumbagin (2) : To plumbagin (200 mg) in glacial acetic acid (4 ml) and fused sodium acetate (200 mg) a mixture of bromine (6 drops) in acetic acid (4 ml) was added. The flask was stoppered and allowed to stand for 8 days. The mixture was poured into ice cold water and extracted with ether (2 × 150 ml). The combined ether layer was washed with water and dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄. The residue obtained was recrystallised from alcohol to yield (2) (284 mg), m.p. 184°; ν_{\max} 3400, 1660, 1640, 1610, 900, 830, 800, 720 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 261, 428 nm; δ (ppm) 2.12 (3H, brs, CH₃), 6.69 (1H, s, H-3), 7.60 (1H, d, H-8), 7.90 (1H, d, H-7), 13.27 (1H, brs, 5-OH).

3-Chloroplumbagin (3) : To plumbagin (250 mg) in acetic acid (15 ml) chlorine gas was bubbled through the solution (1 h; chlorine gas was generated by oxidation of HCl by KMnO₄). Sodium acetate (1 g) was added and heated on a water bath (1 h). The contents were poured into cold water and extracted with ether (2 × 150 ml). The ether layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, evaporated and crystallized from hexane to yield (3) (240 mg), m.p. 125°; ν_{\max} 3350, 1655, 1630, 1610, 870, 835, 740 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 279, 426 nm; δ (ppm) 2.29 (3H, brs, CH₃), 7.32 (1H, m, H-6), 7.75 (2H, m, H-7 and H-8), 12.45 (1H, brs, 5-OH).

5-Acetyl plumbagin (4) : To plumbagin (200 mg) in glacial acetic acid, cooled in ice, conc. H₂SO₄ was added (2 drops). The mixture turned light yellow in colour. It was stoppered and allowed to stand overnight at RT. It was poured into ice cold water and extracted with ether. It was washed with water, dried, over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, evaporated and crystallized from hexane to yield (4) (195 mg), m.p. 118°; ν_{\max} 1760, 1210, 1660, 1620, 1590, 910, 900, 870, 785 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 247, 286, 337 nm; δ (ppm) 2.20 (3H, brs, CH₃), 2.47 (3H, s, 5-OAc), 6.69 (1H, s,

H-3), 7.36 (1H, m, H-6), 7.79 (1H, m, H-7), 8.07 (1H, m, H-8).

Reductive acetylation product (5). (*1,4,5-Triacetoxy-2-methyl naphthalene*) : To plumbagin (200 mg) in glacial acetic acid (3 ml), zinc dust (500 mg), acetic anhydride (5 ml) and fused sodium acetate (500 mg) were added and the mixture refluxed in an oil bath with a calcium chloride guard tube till the solution became almost colourless (30 min). It was filtered, washed with acetic acid and the filtrate was poured into ice cold water. It was extracted with ether (2 × 150 ml), washed with water, dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄, evaporated and recrystallised from hexane to yield a colourless solid (5) (275 mg), m.p. 118°; ν_{\max} 1760, 1670, 1200, 935, 920, 910, 840, 820, 790, 760 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 290, 325 nm; δ (ppm) 2.31 (9H, brs, 1,4,5-OAc), 2.42 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.69 (1H, s, H-3), 7.09 (1H, m, H-6), 7.52 (2H, m, H-7 and H-8).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. Govindarajan, Head, Department of Chemistry, Loyola College and the Director, Central Council for Research in Ayurveda and Siddha, New Delhi for encouragement and support.

References

1. G. V. Satyavati, A. K. Gupta and N. Tandon, "Medicinal Plants of India", I.C.M.R., New Delhi, 1987.
2. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956.
3. G. T. Gujar, *Fitoterapia*, 1990, **61**, 387.
4. S. K. Dhar and P. G. Rao, *Fitoterapia*, 1995, **66**, 442 and the references cited therein.
5. R. G. Cooke, H. David and W. Segal, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1953, **6**, 38.
6. R. H. Thomson, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, **13**, 377.
7. C. H. Collins, "Microbiological Methods", Butterworth, London, 1974.
8. D. K. Pandey, H. Chandra, A. R. Saxena and S. N. Dixit, *Indian Drugs*, 1982, **19**, 459.